

The Lives of the Philosophers and Sophists

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Entry tags: Hellenistic Religions, Neoplatonism, Religious Group, Greek Philosophical Traditions, Text, Hagiography, Ancient Greek text, Greek Religions, Hellenistic Neo-Paganism

The Lives of the Philosophers and Sophists is a compendium of biographies relating to pagan philosophers of late antiquity, perhaps composed in an effort to create an alternative to Christian hagiography. It is characterized throughout by an attitude of traditionalist antiquarianism and hostility towards Christianity, and informed by previous experiments in the genre such as the comparable work of Philostratos. It contains the biographies of Plotinus, Porphyry, Iamblichos, Alypius, Sosipatra, Aedesios of Cappadocia, Sopater, Ablabios, Eustathios, Maximos, Priskos, Ioulianos of Cappadocia, Prohaeresios, Epiphanius, Diophantos the Arab, Sopolis, Himerios, Parnakios, Libanios, Akakios, Nymphidianos, Zeno of Cyprus, Magnos, Oribasios, Ionikos and Chrysanthios, and, likewise, represents one of the latest biographical sources for Neoplatonic intellectuals before the persecutions carried out under the auspices of the Theodosians. It also contains evidence for the practices of Greco-Roman religion in the fourth century, as well as the reactions of its educated practitioners to marginalization and persecution in a Christianized Roman Empire.

Date Range: 347 CE - 414 CE

Region: Eastern Roman Empire (300-600)

Region tags: Southeastern Europe, Middle East, Syria, Asia Minor, Eastern Mediterranean, Thrace, Levant, Greece, Egypt

Late Roman - Early Byzantine Empire (300-600)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Philostratus, Eunapius, 'Lives of the Sophists. Eunapius: Lives of the Philosophers and Sophists', Wilmer C. Wright (ed. and trans.), Loeb Classical Library vol. 134 (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1921)
- Source 2: Robert Penella, 'Greek Philosophers and Sophists in the Fourth Century A.D.: Studies in Eunapius of Sardis' (Leeds, 1990)
- Source 3: Han Baltussen, 'Eunapius' Lives of the Philosophers and Sophists: Was He Constructing "Pagan Saints" in the Age of Christianity?', in Evangelia Anagnostou-Laoutides and Kenneth Parry's (eds.) Eastern Christianity and Late Antique Philosophy (Leiden, 2020), 239-260

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.oxfordreference.com/display/10.1093/oi/authority.20110803095800537;jsessionid=C538BD827AF66BB22CE852E>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: N/A

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked
– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper
– Specify: Animal Membrane

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: No it was not altered

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Hagiography

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: N/A

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– I don't know

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Notes: The text writes from a Neoplatonic viewpoint, the metaphysics of which informed those of Christianity, Rabbinical Judaism, and other contemporary religious practice in the Mediterranean World.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– I don't know

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: N/A
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: It is an unknowable Platonic principle expressed through emanations worshipped as deities.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - I don't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
 - I don't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
 - I don't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: They are not described as such, but rather appear obliquely in the narrative as something which exists and which the characters may interact.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized hierarchically?
 - Yes
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other organization of pantheon?
 - Specify: No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– I don't know

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Paranormal?

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– I don't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Strongly present & highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– I don't know

↳ Courage (in battle)

– I don't know

↳ Courage (generic)

– I don't know

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

- I don't know
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - I don't know
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - No
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - I don't know
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - I don't know
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - I don't know
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - I don't know

- ↳ Strength (physical)
– No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– No
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– I don't know
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No
- ↳ Other important virtues
– I don't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– I don't know

↳ Tragedy?

– I don't know

↳ Epic entertainment?

– I don't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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